

Memorandum for sharing data and information within the LTER-Italy network

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Rationale

This document defines the policy and the rules for sharing and accessing data produced by the Italian Long-Term Ecological Research (LTER-Italy) network. The policy aims at ensuring the diffusion of ecological data, making them as much “FAIR” (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)¹ as possible within the scientific community and the generic public.

LTER-Italy belongs to the European (LTER-Europe) and International (ILTER) networks since 2006. Since 2018, LTER-Europe is enclosed in the ESFRI roadmap toward the creation of the eLTER Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI). LTER-Italy involves many national scientific institutions, universities and public and private agencies performing long-term ecological research in permanent sites, from the terrestrial, freshwater and marine domains, representative of the main Italian ecosystem types. The updated list of research sites is available at the section dedicated to LTER-Italy in DEIMS-SDR (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and Dataset Registry)², the official site and data registry of ILTER. DEIMS-SDR is an information management system that allows to discover LTER sites around the globe, along with the data gathered at those sites and the people and networks associated with them.

LTER aims at better understanding, analyzing, and monitoring the status and changes of ecosystem structure, patterns and processes and biodiversity over extended time periods, typically decades.

With this document, LTER-Italy sustains “open science” as an umbrella concept aiming to remove the barriers for sharing any kind of output, resources, methods, or tools, at any stages of the scientific research processes that are largely, if not exclusively, funded by public money. As such, open access is fostered for research and monitoring data, software, papers, dissemination and communication materials, peer review process, involvement of citizens, etc.

LTER-Italy data policy aims to be consistent with national and international policies or regulations adopted by funding agencies, projects, and RIs. In particular, applicable policies or regulations are those linked to United Nations (UN) conventions, policies of international bodies, and European Union (EU). Moreover, the data policy is intended to be fully compatible with the Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on public access to environmental information [1] and with the INSPIRE Directive [2]. This document is inspired also by the data policies of eLTER RI [3], RITMARE [4], WMO [5], and GEOSS [6].

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² <https://deims.org/network/7fef6b73-e5cb-4cd2-b438-ed32eb1504b3>

The data management in each LTER site is a responsibility of the respective managing institution and this may generate high heterogeneity in the data management procedures and tools. The implementation of mechanisms and workflows for data integration, harmonization and accessibility is therefore a challenging priority within the development of the eLTER RI common data sharing infrastructure.

The life cycle of research data in ecology consists of different phases: acquisition, curation, publishing, processing, and use. Completing the full cycle produces many benefits for different end-users and stakeholders, including the research community itself, policymakers, environmental managers and the generic public. Furthermore, an increased emphasis on openly data sharing has the potential to influence all the phases, stimulating new approaches to data collection, analysis, validation, discovery, and management. Reinforcing open, transparent and robust research approaches that enables the re-use and combination of datasets from multiple sources lays the foundation of all these processes.

Considering all the above-mentioned issues, LTER-Italy adopts a data policy founded on three main principles:

1. data of publicly funded research are a public asset, produced in the public interest and should be made openly available with as few restrictions as possible, timely and following the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)³;
2. data policies and management plans should be in accordance with relevant standards and community best practices. Data with acknowledged long-term value should be preserved and remain accessible and usable for future research;
3. data citation improves the visibility of the network and the scientific impact of LTER researchers including those mainly involved in data collection.

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

Data type

Data collected within LTER-Italy community are generally related to observation of ecological processes, biodiversity and ancillary parameters, including *in-situ* or remote measurements (in general terms “earth observation”). Data can be measured with automatic instrumentations and sensors or manually collected by researchers and technicians.

Within LTER-Italy, datasets include two data typologies:

- 1) data created directly from research activities such as experiments, analyses, surveys, measurements, recordings and observations;
- 2) data resulting from automated or manual data processing, including the inputs and outputs of simulations and models.

In particular, LTER-Italy aims at sharing data from:

- environmental, ecological, biological and biogeochemical data and/or measurements collected manually and/or by automated instruments;
- abundance, biomass and taxonomic composition of species, populations and communities, observed by humans or automated instruments;
- meteorological and oceanographic observations collected by fixed observatories, automated instrumentation and sensor measurements during field surveys or permanently operated;
- measurements collected as a ground true validation of remote sensing observations or products derived from satellite images elaboration.

Nevertheless, this data policy can be considered of general value, hence, it can be applied to any other types of data collected by the LTER-Italy members.

In LTER-Italy, for site level data, the providers and the site managers/owners guarantee for quality and validity of the data.

ILTER-Italy Data Policy

Terms definition

A data provider is an entity belonging to LTER-Italy (person, institution or legal entity) that shares a dataset through the eLTER RI ICT facilities [7, 8].

A dataset is defined as a collection of data generated by a data provider.

Data must be supported by sufficient contextual information (metadata) to enable users to find which research data exist, why, where, when, how they were generated, and how to access them. This information should be made available with terms that permit data full re-use.

A user is an entity (person, institution or legal entity) that requests the use of any dataset shared by LTER-Italy through the eLTER RI ICT facilities [7, 8].

LTER-Italy, directly or in cooperation with eLTER RI, provides some tools (e.g. GET-IT [9], DEIMS-SDR [10, 11], DIP [12]) to facilitate data curation and distribution. LTER-Italy members are strongly encouraged to use these facilities or share data through their proprietary tools, following the best practices proposed in the framework of eLTER RI [9]. Currently, these services are mainly focused on data with geospatial features, which are a substantial part of the ecological data produced by the LTER community.

In this context, LTER-Italy suggests to each site manager a list of rules and guidance for data sharing intended to be applicable at any datasets or products provided by any LTER-Italy research site.

1. The intellectual property of the data shared by a data provider remains exclusively to the provider. Data provider is the unique responsible for the data provided by him/her/itself, for any copyright infringement, as well as any violation that may result from the production of data from sources under the proprietary right of any other person or entity.
2. Metadata and data access, as well as their use, may be subject to different levels of restriction:
 - a.* metadata are always freely accessible, without any restriction, through the tools provided by eLTER RI;

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- b.* LTER-Italy default data access and usage license agreement for all datasets is a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 International) license [13];
 - c.* individual data providers have the option to define their own data usage policy, indicating the restriction level for data usage, which must be anyway consistent and not contrasting with the principles of the LTER-Italy Data Policy, and with what specified at points *d* and *e*;
 - d.* upon request of data providers, access to data may be subject to an embargo period (maximum of one year). Only under particular conditions, data providers may request a longer embargo period. During the embargo period, only metadata will be fully available;
 - e.* sensible data (e.g. occurrence of endangered species) may be subject to additional restrictions that will be negotiated between individual data providers and LTER-Italy.
 - f.* data collected under specific projects or framework which set particular data policy (e.g. from fully open to differing restrictions) can be subjected to *ad-hoc* agreements.

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- [13] Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>)